

ID	Subject Type	Experience Domain	Number of Year
IT_1	Industrial practitioners	Software Architecture and Safety Engineering	>11
IT_2	Experts working with industrial projects	Software Arctecture, Reference Architecture, and SoS	>11
IT_3	Experts working with industrial projects	Safety-critical System and SoS	>11
IT_4	Industrial practitioners	Software Systems Engineering	>7
IT_5	Industrial practitioners	Program Management	>9
IT_6	Industrial practitioners	Senior Eletrial Engineering	>5
IT_7	Experts working with industrial projects	Software Testing and Agile Development	>11
IT_8	Experts working with industrial projects	Requirements Engineering	>40
IT_9	Industrial practitioners	Software Engineering, Project Management and research at Mobile Telecommunication	>15
IT_10	Industrial practitioners	Software Engineement	>13
IT_11	Experts working with industrial projects	Software Testing and Software Quality Management	>40
IT_12	Experts working with industrial projects	Software Architecture	>12
IT_13	Industrial practitioners	Genetical enhancement	>13
IT_14	Industrial practitioners	Agricultural robotics and Research and Development	>30
IT_15	Experts working with industrial projects	Institutional economics	>29
IT_16	Industrial practitioners	Modeling and Simulation	>10
IT_17	Industrial practitioners	Agricola Control Analysis	>24
IT_18	Industrial practitioners	Agricultural Technical	>37
IT_19	Experts working with industrial projects	Software Quality Management and Software Engineering	>40
IT_20	Industrial practitioners	Company Management	>12
IT_21	Industrial practitioners	Innovation Management Engineering	>6
IT_22	Industrial practitioners	Information Technology Consultant	>36
IT_23	Industrial practitioners	Software Architecture	>14
IT_24	Experts working with industrial projects	Self-adaptive System	>8
IT_25	Experts working with industrial projects	Software Product Line and Software Product Family	>30
IT_26	Experts working with industrial projects	Software architecture	>8
IT_27	Experts working with industrial projects	Requirements Engineering	>15